

ON THE PROCESS OF IMAGE CREATION WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

REPHOTOGRAPHY USING
MIDJOURNEY AI

CREATe Working Paper 2025/7

JIM BROGDEN
KRIS ERICKSON

CREATe

On the process of image creation with artificial intelligence: Rephotography using Midjourney AI *

Jim Brogden and Kris Erickson **

Abstract

When we make images using text-to-image AI systems like Midjourney, what precisely are we making? In the context of significant cultural, political and legal uncertainty about the status of AI-generated imagery, this paper reports on a practical experiment in rephotography. The authors attempted to recreate four notable American photographs in Midjourney: Vivian Maier's Untitled self-portrait (circa. 1954), Gregory Crewdson's Untitled (Twilight), (1998-2002), Dorothea Lange's Migrant Mother, Nipomo, California (1936), and Joe Rosenthal's Flag Raising on Iwo Jima (1945). The practice of rephotography, which seeks on one hand to faithfully reproduce and on the other hand to reveal difference, enables us to compare human and AI-generated photography as practice. We find that the AI system exhibits bias in its default perspective, likely an artefact of training data scraped from the open Internet. Specifically, we find: (1) AI images give prominence to main subjects in a way that appears to reflect a late capitalist, consumer gaze; (2) AI images 'hallucinate' details that reduce human intentionality and control; (3) AI images are detached from the social and historical context that gives human photographs meaning. Despite these striking differences, we consider emancipatory and critical potential for AI imagery as an artform. Creative possibilities present themselves in rendering visible the probabilistic links between datasets, user prompts and outputs.

* Forthcoming as Brogden, J. and Erickson, K. (2025). On the process of image creation with artificial intelligence: Rephotography using Midjourney AI. *Journal of Visual Art Practice*, Volume 24, August-December 2025.

** Jim Brogden is Associate Professor in Creative Practice, University of Leeds, and Kris Erickson is Professor of Social Data Science, CREATE, University of Glasgow.

Introduction

The advent of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has raised questions about the role of human creators in the process of image-making (Taffel, 2021; Chang et al., 2023; Anscomb, 2024). For example, the United States Copyright Office recently declined to register works created using generative AI software (USCO, 2025). Two works, *Zaraya of the Dawn* and *Théâtre D'opéra Spatial*, involved images created using the text-to-image AI software, Midjourney. This software allows a user to specify characteristics of an image using textual prompts, and to adjust resulting outputs with further instructions. The artists in both cases claimed authorship over their images, pointing to the volume, specificity and creativity of their prompts. The USCO disagreed, clarifying that works created with substantial input from AI systems are not eligible for protection under copyright. Like the invisible portion of an iceberg, these debates are evidence of deeper cultural anxiety about the impact of generative AI on the creative process, and the meaning of art made with computers.

Some creators argue that AI systems directly copy their work, leading to damaging conditions for human expression. A flurry of recent cases across multiple jurisdictions assert that AI is having a detrimental impact on traditional creative business.¹ For example, Getty Images has sued Stability AI in the UK and the USA for the unauthorised use of 12 million copyrighted photos and their associated keywords from Getty's image library platform to train Stability's AI system.²

Certain creators are turning to self-help methods to resist what they see as both a moral and economic threat. To protect images from being ingested and used for training, two systems offer some form of protection: *Glaze* adds invisible information to a digital image, disrupting the ability of generative AI to learn and mimic an artist's individual style, whilst *Nightshade* is an offensive technique that can poison image data to confuse and corrupt AI model learning (Shan et al., 2023).

Despite legal and moral objections, the use of AI to produce images is becoming more widespread. AI-assisted imagery has appeared on magazine covers,³ commanded high prices at art auction⁴ and formed the basis of new fashion collections.⁵ Our task in this paper is to address

¹ In Europe: *LAION v Robert Kneschke*, (Hamburg District Court 310 O.22723, 27 September 2024), *Like Company v. Google Ireland*(CJEU Case C-250/25); In the UK: *Getty Images and others v. Stability AI*[2023] EWHC 3090 (Ch); In the USA: *Anderson v Stability AI Ltd.*, No 3:23-cv-00201 (N.D. Cal. Jan 13, 2023), *Dow Jones & Company, Inc. v. Perplexity AI, Inc.* No. 1:24-cv-07984 (S.D.N.Y. Oct 21, 2024).

² Getty has launched parallel lawsuits in the UK High Court: *Getty Images and others v. Stability AI*[2023] EWHC 3090 (Ch); and in the USA: *Getty Images v. Stability AI*No. 1:23-cv-00135 (D. Del. Feb 3, 2023).

³ See: <https://www.cosmopolitan.com/lifestyle/a40314356/dall-e-2-artificial-intelligence-cover/>.

⁴ See: <https://www.theartnewspaper.com/2024/11/08/ai-da-robot-painting-sells-one-million-sothebys>.

⁵ See: <https://www.businessoffashion.com/articles/technology/after-months-of-designing-with-ai-norma-kamali-isnt-looking-back/>.

the question: What are AI images? What is their relationship to previous forms of image-making? And crucially, is there space for human creativity in their production? The criterion of 'originality' in copyright law is useful as a starting point: what 'free and creative choices'⁶ available to human photographers remain present when generating images using AI? We assess these questions through the method of rephotography, by attempting to recreate four iconic photographs as closely as possible, using the AI platform Midjourney. The practice of rephotography, by drawing attention to both verisimilitude and change, is an ideal practice through which to explore the differences between AI and human photography.

The article proceeds in five parts. Part 2 reviews the history of photography's struggle to be recognised and the evolving status of the photographer, recently challenged by the proliferation of AI technology. Part 3 describes our methodology and rephotography approach. Part 4 compares the process of creation of four original photographs using our rephotography approach in Midjourney. Here, we find that the process of rephotography using AI tools is not analogous to photography at all. By separating the artist from the image through a process of probabilistic interpretation, AI-assisted photography emphasizes curation and selection rather than embeddedness in a socio-historical context. Part 5 summarises the findings and concludes with avenues for future investigation of AI image making and its creative potential.

Photography in tension

Contemporary debates about the status of AI imagery are connected to a long history of contestation over the role of automatic technology in image-making; a particular predicament for photographic practice, which struggled throughout the 19th century for recognition as a creative artform. One of the earliest cases to establish authorship in an image was an American case, *Burrow-Giles Lithographic Co. v. Sarony*, concerning a portrait of Oscar Wilde taken by Napoleon Sarony in 1882. The U.S. Supreme Court affirmed that copyright extended to photographic images. Although Sarony used mechanical tools in a studio setting, the court found that by purposefully selecting and arranging elements of the image, Sarony had expressed human creative choices that were beyond a machine's capability. As Cooper and Burrow (2019) illustrate for the UK, photographers' struggle for recognition and copyright has persisted from the 19th Century to the present day. A more recent and influential European case, *Painer* similarly evaluated the ability of a school portrait photographer to imbue a work with originality by making

⁶ In the CJEU case *Eva-Maria Painer v Standard Verlags GmbH and Others* (CJEU Case C-145/10), the court clarified that the threshold of originality for copyright in the EU requires the making of 'free and creative choices', for example in the lighting, positioning and composition of a photograph. See Rosati, E., 2018. 'Why originality in copyright is not and should not be a meaningless requirement.' *Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice*, 13(8), pp.597-598.

'free and creative choices' in the lighting, composition, and arrangement of the photograph.⁷ Even more recently and relevant to the production of work by non-human agents, the *Naruto* case concerned a wildlife photographer named David Slater who allowed a group of macaque monkeys to play with photographic equipment he left out while observing them. One of the macaques captured himself in an arresting image dubbed the 'monkey selfie'. The organisation People for the Ethical Treatment of Animals (PETA) sued Slater in California for copyright infringement on behalf of Naruto the monkey. The U.S. Ninth Court of Appeals confirmed that copyright only applies to works created by human beings, but did not weigh in on whether Slater was the original creator.⁸ Views from European legal scholars found it plausible that Slater had exercised sufficient creativity in arranging the conditions of the photograph to make him the rightful copyright owner (Guadamuz, 2016). In summary, copyright generally recognises creative originality in human photographs. But continual legal uncertainty is characterised by suspicion about the intermediating role of automatic technology and the perception that the human might in some cases take a secondary role in image creation.

Paradoxically, photography has also struggled to challenge the assumption that it captures an objective 'reality'. For example, Berger and Mohr (1982) highlight the temporal separation of the photograph-as-object from any objective reality captured in frame:

The photograph offers irrefutable evidence that this man, this horse and this bridle existed. Yet it tells us nothing of the significance of their existence. A photograph arrests the flow of time in which the event photo-graphed once existed (Berger and Mohr, 1982: 86).

Since Louis Daguerre's 'first' photograph of the *Boulevard du Temple* (1838), photography has been burdened by the responsibility to provide evidential truth. The history of photography is inscribed with impactful innovations, including chemical, technological developments in cameras and optics, the digital revolution, software editing, and now the possibilities of artificial intelligence, all of which have been subject to processes of cultural valorisation and intervention. Need we be reminded of the anxieties and desires caused by the presentation of the *Cottingley Fairies* (1917) incident in which Elsie Wright (1901-1988) and Frances Griffiths (1907-1986) faked the presence of fairies in their disarming garden portraits – a stunt that attracted the attention of Sir Arthur Conan Doyle, himself a devotee of so-called 'spirit photography'. From the Loch Ness monster shot by Robert Wilson in 1934 to the flying saucers of Billy Meier later in the 20th Century, photographic hoaxes persist uneasily alongside more mainstream exhortations about the documentary qualities of photography and the vocation of the photographer. This unease is

⁷ *Eva-Maria Painer v Standard Verlags GmbH* (CJEU Case C-145/10).

⁸ *Naruto v. David Slater* 888 F.3d 418 (9th Cir. 2018).

amplified in current discourses about the dangers of AI as we enter the so-called 'post-truth' era (Yamazaki et al., 2020).

There has never been a golden age of indexical truth in photography. The medium's authority has always been questionable: How is a subject to occupy the frame? And where is their position in the visual hierarchy of the image? These are two fundamental questions concerning the authority of the visual. A vivid example of this problem is to be found in the controversial representations of the indigenous Native American Indians (First Nations), in which the 'imperialism' of the frame is made culpable in a form of mythmaking, implicating survey photographers such as William Bell and Timothy O-Sullivan in an inadvertent form of cultural genocide by promoting the notion of uninhabited new territories, to facilitate the expansion of white settlers (Brogden 2019).

The arrival of new technologies and creative possibilities in the mid-twentieth century continued to undermine photography's evidential claims. There have been numerous examples of chemical re-touching, including the infamous 'disappearing' of Trotsky from a photograph of Stalin's speech on May 5, 1920. More recently, Photoshop's arrival in the 1990s introduced the ability to digitally edit photographs. The *Los Angeles Times* famously sacked its battlefront photographer, Brian Walski for altering the position of a British soldier advising civilians to take cover on the Zubayr Bridge in Iraq, on March 30, 2003, by combining two different shots to produce a more compelling composition. Photography's primary encounter with the subject has always suffered from contestation based on the aesthetic choices made by the photographer; in this sense, the authoritative claims attributed to the act of photography have been affected by the complexity of the formal options available.

Similar questions emerge in relation to AI image generation: is the label of photographer now redundant in favour of operator, user, prompter, algorithm wrangler, or 'vibe coder'?⁹ Such distinctions are important as we witness the transition from optical photographs to computational ones (Taffel, 2021; Ritchin, 2025).

As we describe in the following section, our analytical approach involves the interrogation of the Midjourney generative AI system, to reflect critically on the re-presentation of cultural preconceptions in these reconstituted photographs. At the same time, we are not making claims to objectivity, either in reproducing the 'original' images, nor in the original images themselves.

⁹ 'Vibe Coding' entered the lexicon in 2025 to describe AI-assisted programming, in which a human operator relies less on skill and more on 'vibing' with a capable AI model, to produce complex outputs about which the operator has limited understanding.

Instead, we consider the role of artificial intelligence in producing images, and the possibilities for human photographers/artists to express subjective choices in their production.

Midjourney as 'black box'

Midjourney is an online service that enables users to generate images of all kinds (paintings, illustrations, photographs, diagrams) by entering a textual prompt in a command line. Discussions of generative AI systems like Midjourney have often centred around the extent to which they operate as a 'black box' (Pasquale, 2015; Tredinnick & Laybats, 2023) meaning that their internal processes are either too complex to be predictably understood by the user or purposefully withheld by the provider as a valuable trade secret. Nevertheless, users have enthusiastically adopted generative AI services, with some evidencing apparent skill in using them. A community of 'prompt artists' (Chang et al., 2023) has emerged around tools like Midjourney, offering advice and sharing stylistic tips for getting the most out of the system, which involves mastering the opaque language of prompting and the use of special commands that provide more precise instructions to the AI.

The AI at the core of Midjourney is a text-to-image diffusion model. Diffusion models are trained to resolve an image out of a cloud of gaussian noise, according to probabilities stored in an immense database of weights and relational probabilities linking together text and images. For example, if a user asks for a 'cat driving a moon buggy', the system will pull from its training on millions of text-image pairs describing cats, as well as those depicting moon buggies, and mash the two elements together in a final image. Since the system only probabilistically reproduces elements, it has no logical reasoning capability, resulting in frequent hallucinations and otherworldly situations. That makes Midjourney a useful tool for creative exploration, but an unreliable conveyor of information.

Traditional photographers (and indeed the US Copyright Office) have argued that the black box qualities of generative AI create an insurmountable barrier for human creativity to be adequately expressed in its outputs (Karol, 2024; USCO, 2025). According to Alex Yurenev (2025), writing in his poignant online *Silent Hero Project*, an AI reimagining of his father's experiences in the second world war:

Most machine learning systems are black boxes – they are opaque, with billions of neural parameters, not unlike the human nervous system, so that the actions that result from generative AI are unpredictable even to the engineers and computer scientists responsible for deploying these algorithms (Yurenev cited by Ritchin, 2025, 99)

Yurenev highlights the probabilistic nature of AI output, along with the lack of direct control experienced by the human prompter, suggesting an almost magical autonomy that resides in the imperfections in the AI generative process. By contrast, Horning (2024), writing in a special winter edition of *Aperture* magazine on photography's relationship with AI:

Was the photograph ever "real"? "Isn't every photograph unreal to the extent that it is a representation and not something real, in and of itself? Doesn't the term "real photo" remind us of how dubious it has always been to complacently assume that photography objectively documents reality?"

In our exploration of Midjourney, we seek to highlight through a hybrid form of creative collaboration the aesthetic and ideological inner world of AI, involving a process of prompting to re-produce iconic human-authored photographs.

We adopt the practical method of rephotography to draw comparisons between the process of image creation involved in known photographic works, and the process of creation using AI. The results enable us to locate where creative expression and originality – key concepts in Western copyright law – may be found in AI image creation, and to contrast that to claims of authorship made by earlier photographers.

Methodology: rephotography

Rephotography is an established photographic artistic practice, involving repeat capture of a scene from the same viewpoint as an earlier photograph (Bae et al., 2010). Rephotography can be used as a measurement tool in the study of environmental or social change, by capturing longitudinal differences in a single place (Rieger, 2020). We adopt the method to draw attention to the differences in creative practice that emerge by attempting to recreate the same scene using a new technology. Drawing on Roland Barthes' characterisation of photography as both denotative (objective) and connotative (consciously aesthetic), Lewi and Murray (2019) suggest that rephotography is an ideal means of investigating this tension. By creatively re-visiting a scene, the act of rephotography disrupts the calcifying effects of the original scene by drawing attention to both the passage of time and changing social and material conditions in which images are produced.

We adopt a social semiotic approach in this study to analyse the process of re-creation of four iconic American photographs that share a common feature of partial staging in their original production. We have selected these images because they most closely approximate the AI image generation process, in which a user prompts a system with instructions to create a specific scene. The selected images are intentional captures that also result from intentionality of the photographer, highlighted as a key aspect of 'authorship' in western copyright law. Our approach

is social semiotic in the sense that we use textual descriptions to interact with Midjourney, highlighting the importance of linguistics in the prompt sequences; we also draw attention to the distributed nature of our online collaboration, which took place asynchronously between our offices in Leeds and Glasgow. In these collaborative contexts, a social semiotic approach is an appropriate choice for such a performative research enquiry. Moreover, according to Aiello's distillation of social semiotics informed by Kress (2006) and Van Leeuwen (2005), this methodology is concerned with 'the internal structures of texts and, increasingly, also of other semiotic artifacts [...] and semiotic technologies [placing] emphasis on the relationship between form and how people make signs' (Aiello, 2020, 372).

For our rephotography effort, we used Midjourney v6.0 (released in December 2023). The original images were: *Untitled* (circa 1960s) a self-portrait by Vivian Maier, *Migrant Mother, Nipomo, California* (1936) by Dorothea Lange, *Untitled* from Gregory Crewdson's *Twilight* series (1998-2002), concluding with Joe Rosenthal's *Flag Raising on Iwo Jima* (1945). In the following section, we outline the process used to re-create the closest approximation possible to the original images, demonstrating intermediate steps (panels A-D) taken in Midjourney. Some of the attempts (Crewdson, Maier) involved hundreds of prompt revisions and changes to approach, spanning several days, while others took fewer attempts. The purpose of the exercise was to reveal differences in the process of image-making using generative AI compared to traditional photography. And of course, in a social semiotic sense, the exercise inevitably results in new encounters and comparisons with our case study images.

Vivian Maier: *Untitled* self-portrait

The photography of Vivian Maier came to prominence after her extensive collection of over 100,000 previously unseen negatives were found in storage and sold at auction in 2007 to Chicago historian, John Maloof. In a social semiotic sense, how important was John Maloof's intuition in purchasing Vivian Maier's auction lots in the first place? For without Maloof's own social performance – his desire to locate old images of Chicago for a book project, it is uncertain what might have happened to Maier's remarkable archive of dormant negatives, Super-8 films, and obsessive ephemera.

As the compelling documentary *Finding Vivian Maier* (2013) shows, Maloof was driven by the desire to identify the photographer, the enigmatic 'treasure chest' of compelling street photography, and the quest to situate her work posthumously within the history of American photography. As Geoff Dyer reflects in a rather melancholic tone in his foreword 'Geoff Dyer on Vivian Maier', in *Vivian Maier Street Photographer*:

Not only was she entirely unknown to the photographic world, hardly anyone seemed to know that she even took photographs [...] and apparently had no close friends – it also says something about the unknowable potential of all human beings (2011, 8).

We discover through Maloof's focused detective work, that Maier was a nanny in various households, and that her photographic practice was performed under the apparent decoy of making sure that young children 'should be out and about'. In the circumstances, the children became unknowing assistants in the staging of these unforgettable portraits of everyday citizens, complicit in these surreptitious acts of street photography.

Maier's *Untitled* self-portrait [Figure 1] is among many imaginative self-portraits produced over her career. We observe a preoccupation with formal concerns: the familiar trope of self-reflection, through the material reflective surface, a retail shop window becomes a public mirror. Maier employs a casual adoption and subversion of 'window-shopping' to add to her existing repertoire of formally imaginative self-portraits. These outdoor retail self-portraits are perhaps more poignant from a social semiotic perspective because we are aware of those outside of the frame: the children made to wait unsupervised for a moment whilst the photograph is taken. As Gunther Kress reminds us in the axiomatic maxim: 'without frame - no meaning'. In this sense, we cannot unknow what is outside this encounter: the depth-of-field is controlled in such a way by Maier that the twin lens Rolleiflex becomes a central offering, a metonymic device more direct and personal than Maier's upward stare. Unlike the self-portraits of Rembrandt, Van Gogh, Egon Schiele, Frieda Kahlo, and the more performative self-portraits of Cindy Sherman, Maier's self-portraits appear like visual calls for help, a way of working through a personal narrative and isolation. Even these revealing self-portraits are guarded in their preoccupation with the formal concerns of picture making, illusionism, and the recording of place.

Figure 1: Untitled self-portrait (circa 1960s) Vivian Maier.

We begin our rephotography process by attempting to see what elements from the original image the AI system can be placed in the frame with minimal textual description. We also attempt to set the aspect ratio and film type as closely as possible to the original. Of course, Maier's Rolleiflex produced film negatives in a 1:1 aspect ratio, which we specify using the Midjourney prompt syntax '--ar'. Midjourney will reproduce some aspects of common film stocks and focal lengths when instructed to do so, but the effects are more pronounced when prompting well-known examples, since more obscure film stocks will be underrepresented in the training data. We first instructed Midjourney with the prompt to create a:

black and white photograph of a middle-aged woman wearing an old-fashioned dress and sun hat, holding a box camera at waist level. City buildings and a passer-by in background, photorealistic --ar 1:1

This yielded the result shown in *panel A*. The term 'photorealistic' was added on the advice of Midjourney users who reported that it adds a more life-like quality to images that can otherwise appear more cartoonish or computer-generated. The first image lacks several important

elements: the subject is posing as if being photographed by someone else and holding the camera off centre. The manufacture of camera is generic and wrong. There is no sense of a glass reflection between the subject and the camera. The subject is also portrayed glamorously, even though that was not specified in the prompt, likely a vestige of bias in the training data towards more glamorous rather than ordinary subjects. For the next step, we attempted to specify the make of the camera and add glass reflection to obscure the subject and add complexity to the image. We used the prompt:

black and white photography of a middle-aged woman wearing an old-fashioned dress and sun hat, holding a Rolleiflex TLR camera at chest level. City buildings and passers-by in background, photorealistic, double reflection in glass --ar 1:1

This image serendipitously corrects the frontal pose of the subject and improves the accuracy of Maier's camera. However, the subject is still glamorous in terms of dress and appearance, and the setting is more contemporary than the original image. We attempted to solve this by adding more detail to the prompt:

grainy black and white photography of a frowning middle-aged woman wearing an old-fashioned dress and sun hat, holding a TLR camera at chest level, directly facing the camera, drab clothing, double reflection in glass, no makeup, 1960s. City buildings and passers-by in background, photorealistic, double reflection in glass --ar 1:1

By specifying a 'frowning' subject, this reduced the glamorous aspect of the second image while retaining the frontal pose and other elements. The glass reflection is more subtle in this version, possibly because the instruction comes at the end of the prompt. Midjourney weights the probability of elements appearing in an image based on their position in the order of instructions and their frequency. We tried to restore the reflection and arrange it in a manner similar to Maier's original, which frames her own figure with multiple subtle reflections. After much experimentation and multiple attempts, we achieved a satisfactory result using the prompt:

Grainy black and white self-portrait photograph of a thin working-class woman wearing a sun hat, holding a square Rolleiflex TLR camera at waist level and looking straight ahead. City buildings and passer-by in background, photorealistic. Gritty street photography in the style of the 1960s. Reduce the very subtle and imperceptible double reflection in glass --ar 1:1

This resulted in the final image *panel D*. We used the descriptor 'working class' to avert Midjourney away from more glamorous clothing and make-up on the main subject. We repeated 'grainy' and 'gritty' to add more simulated film grain to the image, but this was only partially successful. The final image is a variation on a different image in which the glass reflection was overpowering of the main subject. By reducing the effect, we were able to approximate the centrality of the main subject, but not with as much purposeful framing and artistry as Maier's original image.

Figure 2: Midjourney outputs at intermediate steps A-D.

A dream within a dream: Gregory Crewdson's *Untitled* (1998-2002)

Influenced by his father's psychoanalytical sessions as a youth, Crewdson's imagination and sensibility was deeply affected by the 'dreams of his neighbors', a magical encounter that 'made the space of the urban and suburban into an unearthly and terrifying arena of possibility' (Moody, 2002:6). Crewdson's preference for Freud's essay on the 'uncanny', in which the dormant subconscious emerges, has resonance in relation to his pursuit of a haunted, dream-like iconography and narratology, an apparition not dissimilar from the visual responses offered by Midjourney generative AI. This oneiric mood is pervasive in the photograph *Untitled*(1998-2002) from Crewdson's *Twilight* series echoing inadvertently perhaps, the pedagogic work of Sprott (1996), on the significance of the term 'twilight' in the field of physics, one describing a dreamy state, an absence of perceived reality.

The photograph *Untitled*, (1998–2002)[Figure 3] from Crewdson's *Twilight* series clearly alludes to the painting *Ophelia*(1851-1852) by the Pre-Raphaelite painter, Sir John Everett Millais, itself, an elaborate staged painting involving the model, Elizabeth Siddal, posing in a cold bath, thereby risking hypothermia in the process. Both images share a latent erotic and tragic mood of acceptance. In reference to the Crewdson image, many critics were concerned by the conflation of sexuality and the suggestion of suicide. One is also reminded of the Sofia Coppola film, *The Virgin Suicides* (1999), in which teenage sisters commit suicide enveloped stylistically in a resigned Romantic aestheticization.

Crewdson's lavish reimagining of a suburban Lynchian 'shipwrecked' interior continues his homage to a particular American cinematic framing and mood. The synthesis of artificial and natural light sources, once again, registers his knowledge of Rene Magritte's work, in the juxtaposition of night and day effects. This unsettling 'equinox' emulates the remembering of dreams in which the dichotomy of day and night is often playfully unresolved. Moreover, Crewdson's visual narrative provides a complex semiotic surface to analyse, prefiguring in many ways the text prompts required by generative AI and the subsequent formal outcomes: we notice that the figure is placed in a central position, and the props list used in cinema are all present, including the style of diaphanous dress, the period interior décor, directional and ambient light sources. The numerous visual clues to an epiphanic suicide conveyed by the woman's tranquil stare are distributed across the surface of the photograph, including the discrete glass of water, the pill jar, a clock frozen at 5.10am.

Figure 3: Untitled. From the Twilight series (1998-2002) by Gregory Crewdson.

Starting the process of recreating this image in Midjourney, we attempted to include all relevant objects in the frame and to specify the image aspect ratio. It is likely that Crewdson used an 8x10 large format camera and Portra 160 colour film to produce these images (Scott, 2021). Our first prompt was:

Color photograph of a woman wearing a white night gown lying on her back in a flooded living room, mirror reflective water, 1960s sofa, stairway in background, indoors, flooded, sunlight coming in through windows, bookshelves, cream patterned wallpaper, still life, Kodak Portra 160 --ar 10:8

This produced an unsatisfactory result (panel A). While Midjourney dutifully flooded the living room with water, the image has an unreal and painterly quality that is more prominent than in the original. Midjourney is also reluctant to place the main subject anywhere other than on the sofa. The staircase, an important element in the original image, is also absent. In our second prompt we attempted to resolve the issue by removing reference to the sofa entirely, depriving the subject of anywhere to sit. Panel B shows the result for the prompt:

Cinematic colour photograph of a woman wearing a wet white night gown lying flat on her back, side profile, in a flooded living room, mirror reflective water, 1960s furniture in background, stairway in background, indoors, flooded, lamp light coming in through windows, bookshelves, cream patterned wallpaper, still life, cinematic, --ar 10:8.

The term 'cinematic' was used on the advice of other Midjourney users, who claimed that it can add a film-like quality to outputs. This prompt did appear to reduce the unreal quality of the first attempt somewhat, although Midjourney has still stubbornly leaned the subject against the furniture and has also over-interpreted the word 'lamp' by adding 5 of them to the scene. After dozens of attempts, we found that Midjourney would more readily move the subject to the flooded area if we specified that she was not human but a mannequin. This could be due to safety guardrails put in place by the model developers to prevent harmful imagery, another factor shaping expressive choices. The paradoxical result is that by objectifying the main subject, we can obtain more verisimilar results to Crewdson's original. *Panel C* shows the result of our refined prompt:

Cinematic colour photograph of a female mannequin lying flat on its back, dressed in a wet white night gown, arms by side, looking up, floating on back, side profile, in a flooded 1960s living room, mirror reflective water, 1960s furniture in background, stairway in background, indoors, flooded, lamp light coming in through windows, bookshelves, cream patterned wallpaper, still life, cinematic, --ar 10:8.

We repeat the words 'floating on back' several times to emphasize the pose in the original photograph, but the results are still imperfect, with Midjourney presenting the subject's face turned towards the camera. The lamps are now lit and more realistically placed, but there is still no staircase. After dozens of more attempts, we refined our prompt to successfully include stairs, by changing the wording to 'staircase'. *Panel D* shows the final result from the prompt:

Cinematic colour photograph of a female mannequin floating on back, sleeping on back, dressed in a wet white night gown, arms by side, looking up, floating on back, side profile, in a flooded 1960s living room, suburban house, mirror reflective water, 1960s furniture in background, staircase in background, indoors, flooded, lamp, golden hour light coming in through windows, bookshelves, portraits hanging on wall, cream patterned wallpaper, still life, cinematic, --ar 10:8.

By asking Midjourney to depict the subject 'sleeping' instead of floating, we were able to achieve a closer subject placement with the face turned away from the camera. Again, this may be a result of safety guardrails or a bias towards subjects facing the camera present in the training data. The golden hour light more closely approximates the tone of Crewdson's original, but the patterned wallpaper and hanging portraits are still missing after over 130 attempts and numerous unsuccessful methods of refinement.

Figure 4: Midjourney outputs at intermediate steps A-D.

Dorothea Lange's *Migrant Mother*, Nipomo, California 1936

Dorothea Lange's *Migrant Mother, Nipomo, California* (1936) [Figure 5] was produced in the context of a Farm Security Administration (FSA) assignment, to represent the American rural depression. Some years later, Lange described the initial encounter with the eponymous *Migrant Mother*, Florence Owens Thompson, declaring that she 'saw and approached the hungry and desperate mother, as if drawn by a magnet. I made five exposures, working closer and closer from the same direction.' (In an interview conducted in the 1970s Thompson would contradict Lange's recollection of their meeting, insisting that there had been no conversation).

What is telling in Lange's account of the meeting and photograph, is the apparent reluctance to admit to any specific art direction instructions given to Thompson, to turn the children's faces behind, a 'staging' to dramatically emphasise the lone mother's predicament. Critics have argued that the photograph remains outside the documentary tradition, due in part, to its staging. To reconcile this ethical debate, Gordon suggests that Lange 'was after what she considered a

deeper truth' (2014:30). And of course, we recognise that this element of coercion and staging echoes the longstanding debates surrounding authenticity, and the evidential claims attributed to photography. We may regard this prescient dilemma in relation to the merging of fictional interventions to enhance the socio-political agenda of some forms of contemporary documentary and photojournalistic projects, compounded (as we explore here) by the impact of the generative AI 'scraping' of existing datasets which reveal an algorithmic cultural and ideological global bias.

In subverting the original FSA assignment, Lange memorialises the unique 'landscape' of the human face, revealing its fears, innocence, awkwardness, doubt, stoicism, and authentic beauty. To a contemporary audience the image is invested with a pervasive art photography aesthetic, evocative in the capturing of a specific historical period, whilst providing an implicit narrative quality. The enduring appeal of this iconic image of motherhood is heightened perhaps, by its contrast with Western preoccupations with cosmetic enhancements, the pursuit of youthful beauty, and personal ambition.

Importantly, this is one of numerous portraits of people in the landscape that adopt Lange's 'Madonna' pyramid framing strategy. Lange's formal approach might explain her ability to transform the everyday into the epic, a formal characteristic present in Vivian Maier's portraits. According to Gordon, 'in truth Lange constructed her photographs as much as any painter constructs paintings, and her primary drive was to expand the range of photographic art' (2014: 5). Interestingly, Lange continued after the success of *Migrant Mother* to document with a compassionate lens the internment of Japanese Americans, whose images were censored until its publication in 2006.¹⁰

¹⁰ See: Gordon, L., & Okihiro, G.Y., 2006. *Impounded: Dorothea Lange and the Censored Images of Japanese American Internment*. New York: Norton.

Figure 5: Migrant Mother, Nipomo, California 1936.

Our rephotography effort centered on the main subject and two children, since limited environmental context is present in the original image. Our first attempt provided very bare information to Midjourney, resulting in the image in *panel A*:

black and white photograph of a pensive rural mother evicted from farm with two young children turning their back on camera. --ar 4:5.

Midjourney interpreted the rural setting by placing farmland in the background and giving the family threadbare clothing. As with the Crewdson image, Midjourney stubbornly faces subjects directly towards the camera, even when instructed not to do so. We attempted to add more emotion to the main subject's face and take more control over the pose of the subjects. Panel B shows the result of our prompt:

black and white photograph of a pensive rural mother evicted from farm, looking to the left with two young children hiding their faces at her back, dirty faces, grainy, --ar 4:5.

Next, we attempted to get closer to the specific clothes and setting of the original photograph. We added more specific instructions in *panel C*:

black and white photograph of a pensive rural mother evicted from farm, looking to the left with hand on cheek, two young children hiding their faces away from camera behind her back, dirty faces, gingham shirt, tattered clothing, lines in forehead, worried expression, grainy, --ar 4:5.

Since Dorothea Lange was a highly celebrated and important photographer, we wondered if Midjourney would be able to identify her style and apply it to the prompt. We asked it to produce the image 'in the style of Dorothea Lange' and the results are shown in *panel D*. There are unmistakable similarities to the original image in the pose, clothing and expression of the main subject. However, the indistinct background has been replaced with wooden siding, and the children's faces are still half-visible.

Figure 6: Midjourney outputs at intermediate steps A-D.

By invoking the command ‘in the style of...’ we have found a shortcut to achieving greater verisimilitude to well-known images that are likely to be reproduced in the training data. This type of command works with other notable photographers’ styles, such as Annie Leibovitz and Stephen Shore. At the time of our experiment, it did not work with the images by Vivian Maier and Gregory Crewdson, suggesting that their work had avoided inclusion in sufficient quantity to influence the AI system. A question arises, to what extent is Midjourney copying the photography of Dorothea Lange? The model has clearly been trained on Lange’s work, in the way that outputs match the facial expression, hand placement, and even the clothing of the main subject without detailed instruction to do so. Here we are dealing with probabilities, in which the model may be ‘overfitted’ to connect those specific visual elements with the specific words linking the image to the original photographer (see ‘membership inference attacks’ outlined by Huang et al, 2024). The extent to which such models memorise and reproduce specific images is currently the topic of numerous court cases in the USA, Europe, and the UK, for example, *Getty Images v. Stability AI*, in which output images could be generated that reproduced Getty’s distinctive watermark. Our results demonstrate that a user’s knowledge of a particular style can sometimes be used to manipulate AI output to achieve a specific result that derives at least some qualities from an original body of work.

Raising the Flag on Iwo Jima (1945) Joe Rosenthal

Until recently, the actual circumstances attached to Joe Rosenthal’s iconic photograph, *Raising the Flag on Iwo Jima* taken (February 23, 1945) [Figure 7] had been the cause of much speculation, especially in terms of its alleged ‘staging’ by Rosenthal. As Hammel (2018) clarifies, the so-called staging was accomplished inadvertently through a series of military orders and accidental participants, each of whom performed unexpected missions to the summit of Suribachi. The ‘first flag’ was raised by the Marines with little resistance from the Japanese who were still hiding in the volcano’s caves, to avoid the American bombardment. The Marines only concern was to locate a suitable flagpole to attach the flag. A photographer employed by *Leatherneck* magazine took several shots of the first flag raising but missed the raising of the colours whilst reloading his new film. Surprisingly, no one present photographed the first unfurled flag - the first American flag to fly over the first Japanese territory to be conquered in the war.

For our part, the intricate backstory to Rosenthal’s eventual iconic photograph delineates the often-ignored duration, associated incidents, and serendipitous conditions that result in some memorable photographs. It was Major General Keller Rockey who decided that a much larger second flag should be installed on the summit to communicate the successful assault to the

other marines and support vessels as a morale booster. This ensuing second party included the myopic Joe Rosenthal, who at the time, believed he had missed the main event. After the exhausting ascent, Rosenthal recalls in a later interview that:

The fall of this...fortress in four days of gallant marine fighting was a great thing. A good story and we should have good pictures...So in I went, back to more of that slogging thru deep volcanic ash, warily side stepping the numerous Japanese mines... over the brow of the topmost ridge we could spy men working with the flagpole [...]

At the summit, Rosenthal was alerted by the arrival of the second larger flag. According to Hammel, Rosenthal 'moved to the back of the crater, placed his camera on the ground, and frantically piled up some large flat stones and a sandbag to stand on' (2018, 60). His vantage point achieved, and using black -and- white Agfa film in his bulky 4x5 Speed Graphic camera (with settings of F8 and F11; shutter speed at 1/400th a second), Rosenthal instinctively responded to George Schrier's order for both flags to be set in motion. In a later article 'The Picture That Will Live Forever' (co-authored with W.C. Heinz) in the magazine, *Collier's*, on February 18, 1955, Rosenthal describes taking the shot with typical humility:

Out of the corner of my eye, I had seen the men start the flag up. I swung my camera and shot the scene. This is how the picture was taken, and when you take a picture like that, you don't come away saying you got a great shot.

Interestingly, Rosenthal had only taken four exposures of the second flag, including the now infamous 'Gung Ho' group shot, which would become the cause of the staging rumour for the subsequent decades. A casual eavesdropper mistakenly overheard Rosenthal refer to the Gung Ho shot as a 'staged shot' (in which he had offered direction to the members of the group), hence, the rumour spread. This rumour was disseminated by the much-respected *Time* and *Life* war correspondent, Robert Sherrod, who eventually admitted that he was the sources of the staged allegation.

Hammel's own reading of the semiotic impact of the Rosenthal photograph still resonates, in the celebration its enduring 'kinetic power' and allusions to an epic striving (2018, 69). One recognises that even though the photograph was an instinctive response to the moment, perhaps inadvertently, Rosenthal has produced an image that reverberates across art history, especially in relation to the painting *Raft of the Medusa* (1818-1819), by Théodore Géricault, and more recently, in photojournalism, and the infamous *Fight! Fight! Fight!* (July 13, 2024) photograph taken by Evan Vucci, featuring a defiant Donald Trump after the failed assassination attempt at a campaign rally in Butler, Pennsylvania. Each of these images borrow from the visual hyperbole witnessed in heroic figurative sculptures and propogandist monuments.

Therefore, it was not surprising when Rosenthal's photograph was revived through Felix De Weldon's world-famous *U.S Marine Corps War Memorial* (unveiled November 10, 1954) located outside of the Arlington National Cemetery. During an oral history interview, De Weldon reflects on the sculptural nature of the original photograph, one offering 'the perfect classic lines – the pyramidal base, the flagpole caught at a 45-degree angle – to serve, right out of the box, as a template for a massive, heroic sculpture.'

Figure 7: Raising the Flag on Iwo Jima (1945) Joe Rosenthal.

For our first attempt at recreating this iconic image, suspecting that it was already included in the dataset, we wanted to gauge how much training Midjourney had received in the basic elements of the image (US Marines, American flag, Pacific theatre). We used the simple prompt:

black and white photograph a group of US marines raising an American flag on a mountaintop in the Pacific theatre

This resulted in the image in *panel A*. Most of the elements of the iconic original image are already present. The marines, while anonymous and facing away from the camera, appear authentically uniformed for the period, and the terrain is battle worn. In the second series of attempts, we

tried to position the marines in the correct orientation to one side of the flagpole, and more actively holding the flagpole. We also corrected the aspect ratio of the image. *Panel B* shows the results of the prompt:

black and white photograph a group of US marines raising an American flag on a mountain top in the Pacific theatre. Men holding the flagpole from both sides, side view --ar 4:3:

In this version, the men have a more engaged and heroic pose, but they are not focused on the task of raising the flag, so evocatively portrayed in the original. In the third attempt, we tried to coax Midjourney into making a more active scene, by prompting:

black and white photograph a group of exhausted US marines struggling to raise an American flag on a mountain top in the Pacific theatre. Men holding the flag pole from both sides, side view --ar 4:3

This has resulted in slightly more focus on the flag in Panel C, although hallucination has rendered an incorrect number of stars in a more vertical square pattern than the American flag should contain. One soldier is quite actively holding the flagpole as if leading the group. Finally, we emphasised even more the physical struggle of raising the flag, which resulted in the image in *panel D*:

Black and white photograph a group of exhausted US marines struggling to raise an American flag on a mountain top in the Pacific theatre. Men holding the flagpole from both sides, side view. flagpole is angled at 30 degrees, men grasping to raise the pole. --ar 4:3

In this version, the spirit of the original is more closely captured. The AI system has even reproduced the motion blur on the unfurling flag, giving the image a sense of realism the other outputs lack. By repeating the 'grasping', 'struggling' and 'exhausted' elements, the AI system has produced an image closer in overall appearance to the original, although the figures remain more generic and less animated than the original Rosenthal image. There are other giveaways that this is an AI image: the flag is unnaturally fully visible rather than flapping in the wind, as if the system struggles to reproduce anything but a complete, frontal reproduction. The AI also fails to place the men in a coordinated pose indicating collective action. This is the most compelling feature of Rosenthal's original, and what makes it so symbolically powerful. This failure likely stems from AI's lack of reasoning capability. The men in the image do not have agency or specific goals but are rather simulacra placed independently in the scene according to probabilities calculated by the machine.

Rosenthal's original photograph achieves what few images do, by contributing to a culture's aesthetic sense of sacrifice, honour, valour, the hero myth, the preservation and contestation of national identity. In this context, how close do we get to realising the Rosenthal photograph? Our attempts probably qualify as a partial simulacrum in comparison to the original source, in which

a trained computer system dutifully re-animates exhausted flag-raising servicemen in a disembodied recreation of the past.

Figure 8: Midjourney intermediate steps A-D.

Discussion: learning from failure

Although unsuccessful in significant ways, our rephotography exercise reveals much about the inner workings of generative AI and the creative process of using these systems. Three main findings emerge from our experiment: (1) AI images give prominence to main subjects in a way that appears to reflect a capitalist, consumer bias; (2) AI images ‘hallucinate’ details that reduce human intentionality and control; (3) AI images are detached from the social context that gives human photographs meaning. In this section, we discuss each of these findings in more detail.

1. Consumer bias

It became clear during our attempts that outputs showed a bias towards what has been termed ‘generic’ consumer-oriented imagery (Aiello et al., 2023). Aspects such as framing, point-of-view, positioning of the subject, depth-of-field, and lighting, exhibit similarity to commercial

stock photography. Midjourney resisted when prompted for unconventional compositions (for example placing Crewdson's subject on the floor or rendering the American flag only partially visible). The default appearance of female subjects is glamorous, even in unglamorous settings like 1930s dustbowl America. Safety guardrails, engineered controls that limit models' ability to reproduce harmful, hateful or dangerous content, inevitably limit what is possible at the creative margins. Guardrails also enable 'brand safety' on AI platforms, reinforcing a consumerist orientation. We were reminded of Wilém Flusser's prescient advice in *Towards a Philosophy of Photography*(1984), challenging the photographer to subvert the built-in 'apparatus' of aesthetic habits of the camera as machine. In this sense, Midjourney offers similar entrenched characteristics which need to be overcome by successive prompting, or even clever misdirection (such as stipulating a mannequin instead of a human subject).

Deeper understanding of underlying datasets appears key to achieving desired outputs using generative AI. In Midjourney's case, the training data appear weighted towards a youthful online demographic, characterised by lifestyle content, fan art communities, and the social media 'selfie' aesthetic. No matter how much imagery AI developers scrape from the public internet, datasets are unlikely to overcome inherent biases towards the dominant aesthetic promulgated by late capitalism, with its attendant notions of beauty reinforced by advertising, and platforms such as Instagram. For example, in an experiment with AI image generation to produce images about the Russian invasion of Ukraine, Laba (2024) found that the system reproduced generic images 'generalizing the depiction of *this* war to that of *any* war' (p. 1599).

In this context, what kinds of subjects does AI image generation most accurately represent when prompted? Who is excluded, and why? Although these bigger questions are beyond our scope, we can reflect on how rephotography might help to identify and counter algorithmic biases, or indeed, reveal the dormant biases present in the *habitus* (see Bourdieu) of AI systems like Midjourney.

2. Lack of control and hallucination

Related to the above, how much control does the image-maker have over AI outputs? Were we, as users, able to exercise 'free and creative choices'[6] through our prompts? In a social semiotic sense, Midjourney must be cajoled through repetitive prompting into changing its predictable aesthetic preferences, by explicit and insistent directions in relation to composition, scale, depth-of-field, salience, mood, type of camera, and lens. Because Midjourney probabilistically determines the likelihood of a given element appearing in the output based on the order in which it appears in the textual prompt, repeated reminders are sometimes the only way to achieve desired outputs. As of version 6, Midjourney extended the effective prompt length to 350 words,

although the model does not appear to give equal attention to all of them.¹¹ Consider Panel B in Figure 4 of our Crewdson reconstruction. Midjourney has placed no less than five lamps in the scene, responding to the presence of the word 'lamp', but ignoring the related word, 'light'. It is frustrating that the user has little control over the placement of secondary objects in the scene, although Midjourney offers rudimentary tools to add elements by region. Paradoxically, Midjourney constructs an 'average' scene, whilst eschewing unpredictable, heterogeneous, and idiosyncratic outcomes. And yet, each individual output is different, exposing a lack of control by the user over precise aspects of composition and subject. At least for the moment, it appears that generative AI is unable to transcend beyond its own machine apperception, or, in a popular sense, 'think outside the box'.

3. Detachment from social context

A current and likely persistent weakness of AI image generation tools is their lack of reasoning and an inability to perceive logical relationships. In panel A of the Dorothea Lange reconstruction, the system fails to reflect on whether it is appropriate to place a glamorous subject amongst economic devastation. Similarly, the men in the Iwo Jima recreation are overly relaxed, as if the flag has magically raised itself. Human photography is reliant on the positioning of the photographer's body in the scene. The photographer's eye becomes instrumental to semiotically decoding the scene, by placing the subjects in relation to each other and the viewer. This is not possible in the probabilistic environment of Midjourney, unless one brute-forces semiotic meaning through explicit instruction (e.g., 'two children huddled against their mother, faces turned away from the camera'). And even then, due to the limitations discussed above, the results are likely to be frustratingly imprecise. The act of 'knowing where to stand' (Adams, cited in Swift, 2015) or situating oneself in a socio-cultural context is impossible in AI image generation, which is more comparable to postmodern practices of collage or appropriation art. The experience might be compared to a joint and emergent collaboration, although as Anscomb (2024) observes, AI systems currently lack the cognitive capabilities to act as true collaborators. A more accurate account of generative AI might be one of managed serendipity, in which the user makes selective judgements when presented with outputs only partially guided by human intention.

Conclusions and future developments

Our aim with this paper has been to interrogate the opaque and hidden processes that intermediate between a user prompt and an output image in generative AI. We find that

¹¹ See: <https://www.altexsoft.com/blog/top-ai-image-generators/>.

creativity is significantly altered in AI image-making compared to traditional photography. A human photographer can intentionally capture a scene, expressive of semiotic meaning embedded not only in the manifest representation, but in latent social relationships inferred between subjects and viewers. The AI prompt artist, working from an understanding of the way a machine is likely to interpret the order of words in a prompt, guides a probabilistic outcome by revising their instructions and curating the output through selection towards a desired approximation. AI images, like those abundant in late capitalism, are representational surfaces detached from social context. As Ritchin (2025) writes,

Rather than referents, [digitally generated] photographs serve as 'desirents,' the camera and its software, or the image generators, functioning as post-photographic genies that can grant an abundance of wishes to re-make the world in our own image. (Ritchin, 2025)

Recalling the critique by Aiello *et al* (2023) of consumer stock photography, the advent of AI-generated imagery is continuous with processes already underway via global social media, whereby images are paradoxically *desocialized*. New forms of media literacy will be required to confront the myriad challenges from this technological disruption. We might encourage a more sensitive photographic literacy, enjoining the spectator / consumer / prosumer to:

[...] relate to photographs in more sophisticated ways, engaged in deciphering ambiguity and determining essential meanings, rather than accommodating the traditional and somewhat naïve expectation that the photograph should always provide an answer (Ritchin, 2025, 35).

Through our exploration of iconic American 'staged' photographs we found the AI system produced a hypnogogic, half-remembered, dreamworld, one that can only ever resemble reality in an approximate and probabilistic sense. By careful and insistent linguistic prompts, we informed, and tempted AI Midjourney to create its own equivalents of our four case-study images; each version revealing evidence of an underlying aesthetic bias, always in reference to a training dataset whose contents are opaque to the user.

What is evident in our findings, is Midjourney AI's predilection for conventionality, from which an *average* outcome emerges, synthesised from available image sources. The system tends therefore to adopt a framing strategy and a subject positioning preoccupied by a central composition, while embodying a mainstream Western notion of beauty, eschewing irregular visual forms and unconventional compositional approaches.

Trained as it has been on a massive quantity of digital images scoured from the Internet, Midjourney's capability to produce original images might be inhibited by a pervasive ideological adherence to the late capitalist consumer gaze. To offer some solace in view of a potential

dystopian future, we should consider a more sanguine relationship with AI, in which an emancipated spectator might be open to a reflexivity that acknowledges the limitations and bias inherent in generative AI systems, yet mobilizes these same creative possibilities in emancipatory directions. Achieving this, like many things in our technological age, requires digging beneath the surface of automatic systems to identify opportunities for human agency and creative expression.

Acknowledgements

The research reported in this paper has been carried out between the University of Leeds, School of Media and Communication, and the CREATE Centre in the School of Law at the University of Glasgow. This work was supported by the Arts and Humanities Research Council AHRC (grant number AH/Y007662/1).

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Supplemental data

There is no supplementary data accompanying this paper.

References

- Aiello, G. 2020. "Visual Semiotics: Key Concepts and New Directions." *The Sage Handbook of Visual Research Methods* (2nd Edition) (Eds. Luc Pauwels and Dawn Mannay), pp. 367-380. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Aiello, G., Thurlow, C., and L. Portmann. 2023. "Desocializing Social Media: The Visual and Media Ideologies of Stock Photography." *Social Media + Society*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231156363>
- Anscomb, C. 2024. "AI: artistic collaborator?" *AI & Society*, 1-11.
- Bae, S., A., Agarwala., and F. Durand. 2010. "Computational Rephotography." *Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory Technical Report*. MIT-CSAIL-TR-2010-016 CBCL-287.
- Berger, J., and J. Mohr. 1982. *Another Way of Telling*. New York: Pantheon Books.
- Crawford, K. 2024. "Metabolic Images." *Aperture*. New York.
- Brogden, W., J. 2019. *Photography and the Non-Place: The Cultural Erasure of the City*. Palgrave.
- Chang, M., S. Druga, A. J. Fiannaca, P. Vergani, C. Kulkarni, C.J. Cai and M. Terry. 2023. "The prompt artists." In *Proceedings of the 15th Conference on Creativity and Cognition*, pp. 75-87.
- Cooper, E. and S. Burrow. 2019. "Photographic copyright and the Intellectual Property Enterprise Court in historical perspective." *Legal Studies*, 39(1), pp.143-165.
- Dyer, G. 2011. "Geoff Dyer on Vivian Maier." *Vivian Maier Street Photographer* (Ed. John Maloof). Powerhouse Books.
- Eagleton, T. 1990. *The Ideology of the Aesthetic*. Blackwell Publishers.
- Elcott, N, M. 2024. "Generative Style." *Aperture*. New York.
- Flusser, W. 1984. *Towards a Philosophy of Photography*. Reaktion Books.
- Goldmann, N. 1978. *The Jewish Paradox*. Grosset & Dunlap.
- Gordon, L. 2014. *Dorothea Lange: Aperture Masters of Photography*. Aperture Foundation.
- Guadamuz, A. 2016. "The monkey selfie: copyright lessons for originality in photographs and internet jurisdiction." *Internet Policy Review*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.14763/2016.1.398>
- Hammel, E. 2018. *Two Flags over Iwo Jima: Solving the Mystery of the U.S. Marine Corps' Proudest Moment*. Casemate.

- Horning, R. 2024. "Deep Reals: What is realism in the age of artificial intelligence?" *Aperture* Archive.
- Huang, K., B. Goertzel, D. Wu, and A. Xie. 2024. "GenAI model security." In *Generative AI Security: Theories and Practices*, pp. 163-198. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland,
- Karol, P, J. 2024. "Ghosts in the Machine." *Aperture*. New York.
- Kress, G., and T. van Leeuwen. 2006. *Reading Images: The Grammar of Visual Design*, 2nd edn. New York: Routledge.
- Laba, N. 2024. "Engine for the imagination? Visual generative media and the issue of representation." *Media, Culture & Society*, 4(8), 1599-1620.
- Lewi, H. and Murray, A., 2019. Rephotography and the Situating of Then-and-Now. In *The Routledge International Handbook of New Digital Practices in Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums and Heritage Sites*(pp. 397-409). Routledge.
- Moody, R. 2002. "On Gregory Crewdson." *Twilight: Photographs by Gregory Crewdson*.
- Pasquale, F. 2015. *The black box society: The secret algorithms that control money and information*. Harvard University Press.
- Rieger, J. H. 2019. Rephotography for Documenting Social Change. Chater 6. In *The SAGE Handbook of Visual Research Methods*. London: Sage.
- Ritchin, F. 2025. *The synthetic eye: photography transformed in the age of AI*. New York: Thames & Hudson Inc.
- Scott, G. 2021. "Thoughts on Gregory Crewdson." The United Nations of Photography Blog. Accessed online: <https://unitednationsofphotography.com/2021/02/21/thoughts-on-gregory-crewdson/>
- Shan, S., Ding, W., Passananti, J., Wu, S., Zheng, H., & Zhao, B. Y. (2024, May). Nightshade: Prompt-specific poisoning attacks on text-to-image generative models. In *2024 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*(pp. 807-825). IEEE.
- Sprott, C, J. 1996. *Physics Demonstrations: A Sourcebook for Teachers of Physics*.
- Swift, M. 2015. *Ansel Adams: Knowing where to stand*. New York: Chartwell Books.
- Taffel, S. 2021. "Google's lens: Computational photography and platform capitalism." *Media, Culture & Society*, 4(2), 237-255.

Tredinnick, L., & Laybats, C. 2023. "Black-box creativity and generative artificial intelligence." *Business Information Review*, 40(3), 98-102.

Van Leeuwen, T. 2005. *Introducing Social Semiotics*. London: Routledge.

Yamazaki, T., K. Murata, Y. Orito, and K. Shimizu. 2020. "Post-Truth Society: The AI-driven Society Where No One Is Responsible." In *In Mario Arias Oliva, Jorge Pelegrín Borondo, Kiyoshi Murata and Ana María Lara Palma (eds.), Societal Challenges in the Smart Society*(pp. 397-405).

CREATE

Centre for Regulation of the Creative Economy

School of Law / University of Glasgow

10 The Square

Glasgow G12 8QQ

www.create.ac.uk

2025/07 DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16883055](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16883055)

CC BY-SA 4.0

In collaboration with:

**UNIVERSITY
OF LEEDS**

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council